

DAMPING STUDIES IN Al-Li-SiC_p COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Damping characteristics of 8090 Al alloy and its composites reinforced with 8, 12 and 18 vol.% SiC particles were investigated using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA). Tests were done at three different frequencies (0.1, 1 and 10 Hz) over a temperature range of 27 to 300 °C. The damping capacity of the unreinforced 8090 Al alloy and its composites increases with decreasing frequency in the entire frequency range (0.1-10 Hz) used here. Composites show higher damping capacity compared to the unreinforced alloy in the entire frequency and temperature range investigated here. The higher damping capacity of the composites can be attributed to higher dislocation density, grain boundary and interface damping.

KEY WORDS: Damping, aluminium alloys, particulate reinforced composites, dynamic mechanical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Damping capacity is the measure of a material's ability to dissipate elastic strain energy during mechanical vibration or wave propagation. Structural materials that exhibit high damping capacity are useful in the passive attenuation of noise and vibration in structures. This has led the way for development of materials possessing high damping capacity in combination with high stiffness and low density. Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) are one such class of materials. Discontinuously reinforced MMCs are particularly suitable for this purpose since these can be mass produced and also possess excellent mechanical properties [1-3]. In MMCs, damping capacity can be improved by additions of reinforcing phases that possess high damping capacity or by additions that dramatically modify the matrix microstructure in such a way as to increase damping capacity. SiC, Al₂O₃, and graphite are most frequently used reinforcements in these MMCs. Both positive and negative changes in damping capacity with the addition of SiC particles have been reported [4, 5]. There are reports [6, 7, 8-13] of substantial improvement of damping capacity of Al alloys with addition of graphite particles. Composite having combination of SiC and graphite reinforcements (hybrid reinforcements) have also been processed and reported to possess better damping capacity [14-16].

Damping capacity of a material is realized either by decay of vibration amplitude in free motion or by suppression of resonant amplitude and the phase lag of deformation behind the applied load in forced vibration [17]. There are several parameters, which can be used to characterize damping capacity [18]. Specific damping capacity is one such parameter, which is given by the relation

$$\Psi = \frac{\Delta W}{W} \quad (1)$$

Loss tangent ($\tan \phi$) or loss factor (η) is given by [18]

$$\eta = \frac{E''}{E'} = \tan \phi \quad (2)$$

where, E'' is the loss modulus, E' is the storage modulus, η is loss factor and $\tan \phi$ is loss tangent.

Logarithmic decrement $\delta = \frac{1}{n} \ln \left(\frac{A_i}{A_{i+n}} \right)$ and inverse quality factor $Q^{-1} = \frac{f_2 - f_1}{f_r}$ are also used to characterize damping capacity [18].

All the aforementioned quantities are inter related by [18]

$$\psi = 2\pi\eta = 2\pi \tan \phi = 2\pi Q^{-1} = 2\delta \quad (3)$$

Al-Li alloys possess low density and high specific strength and stiffness, which can make them potential candidate to serve as the basis for high damping materials. However, knowledge of damping behavior of Al-Li based composites is very limited. This investigation aims at characterizing the damping behavior and mechanisms of damping in 8090 Al-SiC_p composites processed by stir casting technique. The damping data obtained using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) is discussed on the basis of matrix microstructure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Composite preparation and Microstructural characterization:

The matrix material used in this study is an 8090 Al alloy whose composition is given in Table 1. The composites were fabricated by stir casting technique. The reinforcement is SiC particles of average size 40 μm . Composites containing 8, 12 and 18 volume% SiC were fabricated. Cast billets were then hot extruded in a CBJ 250 T Extrusion press at a temperature of 540 °C with an extrusion ratio of 30:1. Specimens for microstructural characterization and damping measurements were made from the extruded rod. The damping specimens are rectangular bars with dimensions of 2 x 9 x 50 mm.

Sliced samples of composites were first polished with emery papers up to 1200 grit size followed by polishing with alumina paste on a velvet cloth. Finally, the samples were polished with diamond paste to mirror finish. Microstructural characterization of the polished samples was done by SEM and optical microscopy. The morphology, distribution and volume fraction of SiC particles in the composites was determined by standard metallographic techniques. The grain sizes of the alloy and the composites were determined using Sigmascanpro software.

Damping measurements:

Damping measurements were carried out using a GABO Eplexor Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA). The detail experimental procedure of damping measurements is reported elsewhere [19]. The samples were loaded in three point bending arrangement and the loss tangent and elastic modulus were recorded as a function of temperature. Measurements were done at three frequencies, viz, 0.1, 1 and 10 Hz in the temperature range of 27 to 300 °C at a dynamic load of 10 N. The load applied is much below one-tenth of the yield stress of the alloy. The samples were heated at a rate of 5 °C/minute. At least three tests were done at each frequency to verify the repeatability.

Table 1 : Chemical composition of the alloy (wt.%)

Li	Cu	Mg	Zr	Fe	Si	Al
2.14	2.0	0.88	0.12	0.1	<0.03	Bal.

RESULTS

Microstructure:

SEM micrographs in Figure 1 (a) to (c) show the microstructures of the composites in as extruded condition. SiC particles are angular in shape. The distribution of particles in composites is fairly homogeneous.

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of composites in extruded condition showing morphology and distribution of SiC particles (a) Al-Li-8%SiC, (b) Al-Li-12%SiC and (c) Al-Li-18%SiC.

Damping characteristics:

Damping behavior of unreinforced alloy:

Fig. 2 shows the plot of E^* , the elastic modulus, and $\tan \phi$, the damping capacity, vs temperature at different frequencies for the unreinforced 8090 Al alloy. The dark symbols represent elastic modulus (E^*) and the hollow symbols denote damping capacity ($\tan \phi$). Following characteristics can be noted from the graph in Fig. 2. First, the elastic modulus decreases with increase in temperature. The modulus is essentially independent of frequency in the frequency and temperature ranges investigated in this study. Secondly, the damping capacity, $\tan \phi$, exhibits almost no variation with temperature up to about 180 °C except at the lowest frequency used here i.e. 0.1 Hz. The damping capacity at 0.1 Hz increases continuously with temperature. At other frequencies damping capacity increases with temperature beyond 180 °C. Lastly, damping capacity at 0.1 Hz is lower at lower temperatures but beyond the temperature (about 180 °C), at which damping capacity starts varying with temperature, is always higher than those at other frequencies. Therefore it can be said that generally damping capacity of the unreinforced alloy increases with decrease in frequency.

Damping characteristics of Al-Li-SiC_p composites:

Figures 3 (a), (b) and (c) show the modulus and damping capacity vs temperature curves of the composites, which show similar trends as the unreinforced alloy. The moduli of the composites also show similar trend as the alloy. In general, the moduli of the composites decrease with increasing temperature. However, as can be seen from Figures 3 (b) and (c), modulus of Al-Li-12%SiC and Al-Li-18%SiC composites is weakly dependent on frequency. Further, the modulus decreases rapidly at temperature above 270 °C at the lowest frequency used here i.e. 0.1 Hz. The frequency dependency of damping capacity observed here is at variance with previous studies [10-13, 20, 21]. All those studies report that damping capacity is independent of frequency at lower temperatures. In this study damping capacity is found to depend on frequency even at lower temperatures. The composites show higher damping capacity than the unreinforced alloy over the entire frequency and temperature range used in this study. Generally, the composite containing 18 vol.% SiC exhibits highest damping capacity at all frequencies in this study. Table 2 shows values of damping capacity and elastic modulus of unreinforced alloy and composites at four different temperatures at a frequency of 1Hz.

Fig. 2. Damping characteristics of the unreinforced alloy.

Fig. 3. Variations in damping capacity and modulus of composites with temperature (a) Al-Li-8%SiC, (b) Al-Li-12%SiC and (c) Al-Li-18%SiC.

Table 2 : Damping capacity and Elastic Modulus at different temperatures at 1 Hz

Temperature (°C)	Vol. fraction of SiC _p							
	0		8		12		18	
	tan ϕ	E (GPa)	tan ϕ	E (GPa)	tan ϕ	E (GPa)	tan ϕ	E (GPa)
50	0.034	77.6	0.037	87.7	0.046	88.0	0.051	91.0
200	0.041	76.4	0.052	86.1	0.067	87.7	0.065	89.7
250	0.056	75.2	0.067	85.8	0.078	86.4	0.081	87.4
300	0.073	73.4	0.083	83.4	0.090	83.7	0.106	83.4

DISCUSSION

Damping Mechanisms:

As discussed above, composites exhibit higher damping capacity than the unreinforced alloy over the entire frequency range used in this study. The improved damping capacity of the composites is a result of additions of SiC reinforcements and the accompanying modification of the matrix microstructure. Modification includes refined grain size, a high density of dislocations generated due to the difference in coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between reinforcement and the matrix, and a large area of interfaces between the reinforcement and matrix. Among the damping mechanisms that play a role in metals and alloys, thermoelastic and microstructural effects (i.e., crystallographic defects) are most common. Each of these defects has a damping mechanism associated with it. The composites contain most of these defects as a result of modification of the microstructure (due to the presence of reinforcements), and therefore the damping capacity of the composites is directly related to each of these damping mechanisms. In the following discussion these damping mechanisms will be related to the experimental results summarized in the previous section.

Thermoelastic damping:

Thermoelastic damping is caused by the energy dissipated by irreversible heat flow generated by stress-induced thermal gradients [22]. According to Zener thermoelasticity theory [22], the thermoelastic damping increases with increasing frequency as long as the frequencies are less than Zener relaxation frequency. As discussed earlier, in the present study the measured damping capacity of the unreinforced alloy and its composites decreases with increasing frequency over the frequency range used here. From these observations it can be said that frequency dependency of damping capacity in the frequency range used here is not due to thermoelasticity.

Grain boundary damping:

In polycrystalline materials grain boundaries show viscous-like properties. Grain boundary sliding under an applied cyclic stress converts the mechanical energy into thermal energy as a result of internal friction at grain boundaries. The thermal energy is then dissipated by the thermal conductivity of the material leading to higher damping. In particle reinforced MMCs,

particles may possibly help in refining the matrix grain size. The average grain size of the unreinforced alloy in the as cast condition is 48 μm and that of Al-Li-8%SiC and Al-Li-18%SiC are 36 μm and 25 μm respectively. The finer grain size of the matrix due to addition of SiC particles may contribute to enhanced damping capacity of composites.

Interface damping:

Large number of interfaces are created due to addition of reinforcement particles in MMCs. These interfaces also contribute to enhance the damping capacity of MMCs. The contribution of interfaces to damping capacity of a particulate reinforced composite with perfectly bonded interfaces is given by Schoeck theory [23]. According to this theory the contribution of interfaces to high temperature damping is given by the equation

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{4.5(1-\nu)}{\pi^2(2-\nu)} V_p \quad (4)$$

where, where ν is poisson's ratio of the matrix and V_p is the volume fraction of reinforcement. At elevated temperature the interface effect may become more significant because the metal matrix becomes soft relative to the ceramic reinforcement, and a reversible movement at the interface is likely to occur. Here, the poisson's ratio of the 8090 Al matrix is 0.34 and if we take Al-Li-18%SiC_p composite equation (4) yields a value of 0.032 for interface damping which is quite consistent with the observed increase in damping for the composite at higher temperatures.

Dislocation damping:

The mechanism by which dislocations affect damping behavior is given by Granato-Lücke theory [24]. This mechanism assumes that losses occur due to dislocations breaking away from weak pinning points under cyclic loading. This breakaway and sweeping motion dissipates energy in proportion to the area traversed. Material damping is related to dislocations by the following equation

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{C_1}{\varepsilon_o} \exp\left(-\frac{C_2}{\varepsilon_o}\right) \quad (5)$$

where Q^{-1} is the dislocation damping, ε_o is strain amplitude and C_1 and C_2 are material constants; C_1 is proportional to the dislocation density in the matrix. The contribution of dislocation damping decreases with increasing temperature as dislocation density decreases.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Damping capacity shows little or no dependency on temperature up to 180 °C at all the frequencies used except at the lowest frequency of 0.1 Hz where it increases continuously with temperature. Damping capacity at 0.1 Hz is lower at lower temperatures but it is always higher than those at other frequencies at the temperature beyond which damping capacity changes with temperature.
2. Damping characteristics of the unreinforced Al-Li alloy and its composites containing 8, 12 and 18 vol.% SiC were found to depend on frequency even at lower temperatures.
3. Generally, the damping capacity increases with decreasing frequency in the frequency range used here.

4. Composites show higher damping capacity than the unreinforced alloy in the temperature range of 27 – 300 °C and in the frequency range 0.1 – 10 Hz used in this study. This can be attributed to the higher dislocation density, grain boundary and interface damping.
5. The moduli of the alloy and the composites decrease with increasing temperature.

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